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DROWNING IN TRASH
An Urgent Call for Environmental Action

One of the most pressing and alarming issues in the Philippines is pollution, specifically waste management. Garbage is found all over: on our streets, in our rivers, and even bobbing around in our oceans.

This is a direct result of a serious issue: our nation generates huge amounts of waste. According to data from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), "the Philippines daily generates approximately 61,000 tons of solid wastes, of which 24% are plastic waste, including plastic sachets, plastic bags, and packaging materials."

Contrary to expectations, Filipinos use and dispose of substantial amounts of plastic: at least 163 million handy plastic bags, 48 million shopping bags, and 45 million thin-film bags daily. A major chunk of these is dumped in landfills, dumping sites, and other environments; some spill into rivers and ocean bodies. In the Philippines, we are expected to generate a total of 23.61M tons of waste by 2025, which is quite disappointing to hear as a Filipino who wants their country to be safe from the spread of waste.

Given how much waste we generate each day and the estimated amount for 2025, it is high time we learned to manage waste, practice the RS (Reuse, Reduce, Recycle, Repair, and Recover), and join programs to clean up waste.

Scattered garbage is difficult to manage and causes pollution, which can lead to diseases and respiratory problems. It should be prevented at all costs because we cannot just allow it to become normal.

Waste pollution may occur in several ways, including air pollution from burning waste materials for fuel, and aquatic pollution from the disposal of waste in rivers, oceans, and other water bodies. Such activities have negative environmental effects and are a danger to human health, animals, and the environment.

We are not just protecting the environment for ourselves and our community. We are protecting the environment for the community at large. Protecting the community is a responsibility that we share. This is because a dirty community influences the lives we lead. Some effects of a dirty community include disease, environmental destruction, and an unsafe, unpleasant environment.